

Quantum Potential and Kinetic Entropy?

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Classically, Shannon's entropy is given by $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. In the literature (1), this is sometimes applied to quantum mechanics using $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ (and a similar entropy connected with $P(p)$). Thus, a spatial entropy is $-\int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln\{W^*(x)W(x)\}$. One possible issue with such an approach is that for a free particle, $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$, the length L is completely arbitrary and leads to $P(x)=1/L$ which in turn leads to an entropy of $\ln(L)$. We suggest that this entropy does not capture the uncertainty linked to a wavelength, \hbar/p , i.e. the uncertainty linked to a crest of either $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$. We have already discussed in previous notes the idea of taking $|\sin(px)|$ for a crest and normalizing it and then using such a probability for Shannon's entropy.

In (2), we suggested that the notion of crests and troughs for local probability normalization in space holds as well in a system with a potential $V(x)$. If one writes: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + W V(x) = EW(x)$, we suggest that $W(x)$ has crests and troughs of different heights and widths and that one may take the absolute value of each and create a normalized probability for each. This too has been discussed in previous notes.

Here, we wish to consider the average kinetic energy term $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ (without multiplying by W^*) and the term $WV(x)$. If one considers a harmonic oscillator then these two terms also have crests and troughs, albeit distorted ones. We suggest that each may be normalized (using the absolute value as well) to create a probability which may then be used to create a Shannon's entropy expression for each crest or trough. This would then be a kinetic energy entropy or a potential energy entropy per crest/trough, a concept which does not seem to be used in classical physics.

Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's entropy is given by: $S = -\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. As a result, in some cases in the literature (1), a probability $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, is defined and used to create a spatial entropy:

$$S_{\text{spatial}} = -\int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln\{W^*(x)W(x)\} \quad ((1))$$

A similar expression is used to create S momentum using $a^*(p)a(p)=P(p)$ where $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

We suggest that one possible issue with such an entropy is that for a free particle:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad \text{where } L \text{ is an arbitrary length} \quad ((2))$$

Thus, Shannon's entropy becomes: $\ln(L)$ ((3)) which depends only on L and does not demonstrate the spatial uncertainty within a crest of either $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$. In a previous note, we have already suggested using $|\sin(px)|$ and normalizing it for a crest to create

a probability which may then be used to create a Shannon's entropy value which holds for the crest length of $.5 \hbar/p$. For $\exp(ipx)$, this same entropy value holds for each \hbar/p unit.

In the case of a bound state, there are still crests and troughs in $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, at least in a region roughly equal to the length between the classical turning points. In a previous note, we suggested taking the absolute value of each crest or trough and normalizing it to create a probability which could then be used to calculate a crest-specific Shannon's entropy value.

The Notion of Kinetic Energy and Potential Energy Entropy

We suggest that if one accepts the notion of crest/trough specific entropy suggested above, one should be able to create a probability and hence Shannon's entropy whenever a crest or trough appears. For the time independent Schrodinger equation:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V(x)W(x) = E_n W(x) \quad ((3))$$

$W(x)$ has crests and troughs and each describes uncertainty in position within the crest/trough. A kinetic energy expression, $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ (unnormalized) and a potential term $V(x)W(x)$ (which shows the explicit interactions between $V(x)$ and single particle terms of $W(x)$), both contain crests and troughs and so should lead to kinetic energy crest specific and potential energy crest specific entropies.

First, we wish to discuss the physics of the term $V(x)W(x)$ in more detail because formally:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W \quad ((4))$$

$KE_{ave}(x)$ is identical to the classical kinetic energy and does not contain crests and troughs. As a result, one may object to using the form: $V(x)W(x)$. We note, however, that in classical physics, if one has a single particle, then potential energy is $V(x)$, while if one has a density $d(x)$, one has $V(x)d(x)$. In quantum mechanics, one has a density $W^*(x)W(x)$, so in keeping with classical physics, one should really consider $V(x)W^*(x)W(x)$. Given that $W^*(x)W(x) = \text{constant}$ for a free particle, we suggest that one may actually consider $V(x)W(x)$. To see the physical meaning of $V(x)W(x)$, one may write both as Fourier series, i.e.: $\sum_{k,p} V_k \exp(ikx) a(p) \exp(ipx)$. This shows the free particles which comprise $W(x)$ and do not exist at a fixed x receiving impulse hits from $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus, this shows the working of the potential interaction and so seems to be linked with a physical interpretation.

Secondly, we wish to argue that if $W(x)$ has crests and troughs, then $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ and $V(x)W(x)$ may also have crests and troughs. A simple example is the first excited state of a quantum oscillator, $x \exp(-.5\sqrt{k}mx)$. This has a single $W(x)=0$ at $x=0$ and a crest and trough and so $V(x)$ has the same, albeit skewed by $V(x) = .5kx$. For the case of $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$, one still has this value 0 at $x=0$ and again a crest and trough which drop off because $\exp(-.5\sqrt{k}mx)$ dominates for large x .

Thus, we suggest that one may create a probability by taking the absolute value of the kinetic energy and potential energy in each crest/trough and normalizing it. One may then create a kinetic energy and potential energy crest-specific entropy, we suggest.

Conclusion

In conclusion, as argued in previous notes, we suggest that one use a single crest/trough, take its absolute value and normalize it to create a crest specific probability using Shannon's entropy. This holds for a free particle as well as a quantum bound one, whereas $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}=1/L$ which yields an entropy of $\ln(L)$ which does not show the entropy due to position uncertainty within the crest or trough. This same approach applies to a bound state, we argue.

Here we suggest that one should be able to extend this idea to: $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}$ and $V(x)W(x)$, because these kinetic and potential energy type terms still exhibit crests and troughs, albeit skewed ones. As an example, we consider the first excited state of a quantum oscillator. Even though the kinetic energy is $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} /W$ which matches the classical value and does not have crests/troughs, we suggest that using $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + V(x)W(x) = E_n W(x)$ has a more balanced symmetry and that $V(x)W(x)$ has physical meaning because it shows how single particle $\exp(ipx)$ s in $W(x)$ receive impulse hits from $V(x)=\sum \text{over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$.

As a result, we suggest taking the absolute value of $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}$ and WV within a crest or trough and normalizing it to create a probability which may then be used in a crest/trough specific Shannon's entropy expression. We suggest that this represents a kind of crest specific kinetic energy or potential energy entropy which does not seem to be used in classical physics because there are no crests and troughs.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Frequency/Wavelength and the Normalization of Probability Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2024)